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U-Turns in Pakistani Politics: A Complex Game of Political Chess

Khalid Zaman¹

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Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan

***Corresponding author**

Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan
Email: khalid_zaman786@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the occurrence of political U-turns in Pakistan by examining the most prominent politicians and their associated political parties. According to research, the phenomenon of 'political U-turns' has a detrimental impact on Pakistan's development and stability. This tendency also erodes public trust in the government and impedes progress towards improved economic and social conditions. Pakistan's legislators and policymakers must prioritise the country's long-term interests over their individual or party's immediate gains. For governments to secure the backing and trust of their constituents, they must exhibit greater transparency and accountability towards them. Ensuring the expression of individuals' viewpoints necessitates holding elected representatives responsible and actively engaging in the political sphere. This study highlights the imperative requirement for cooperation among all pertinent stakeholders in Pakistan to tackle the problem of 'political U-turns' and promote the nation's stability and progress.

Keywords: Pakistani politics; U-turns; Consequences; Suggestions; Country's stability.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been an increase in the frequency of political 'U-turns' in Pakistan, whereby politicians and political groups frequently alter their positions on contentious issues. The perplexity and exasperation caused by this phenomenon have led to inquiries regarding the dependability and transparency of Pakistan's democratic system. The phenomenon of 'political U-turns' has been attributed to both the ruling administration and the opposing party, resulting in a decline in public trust towards political establishments and democratic governance. Analyzing the reasons and consequences of political U-turns in Pakistan is of utmost importance, as political stability and transparency are indispensable for the sustainability of any democratic system. The objective of this study is to examine the aforementioned trend through an analysis of its underlying factors and resultant impacts on the nation's political terrain.

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The study aims to achieve its objective by addressing the following inquiries:

1. To examine the reasons behind the tendency of politicians in Pakistan to alter their stances on controversial issues and to analyze the impact of this phenomenon on the political structure.
2. What measures can politicians and policymakers in Pakistan take to address this issue and promote greater transparency and trust in their government?

This research aims to elucidate the issue of 'political U-turns' in Pakistan and offer recommendations to policymakers and political figures for its resolution through a comprehensive analysis. This study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges facing the democratic system in Pakistan and to support efforts to enhance institutional trust and transparency.

2. Literature Review

It is common vernacular in Pakistani politics to criticize politicians who change their opinions by using the phrase "U-turn." This term has been used to describe politicians from the PTI, PML-N, and the PPP. According to an article published in Dawn by Raza (2018), the PTI government has implemented more policy changes than any other in Pakistan's history. The nation's political climate often features policy "U-turns" or reversals by the administration. The author maintains that reversals may be beneficial, especially in Pakistan, where things are changing so fast. To encourage compromise and lessen the chances of conflict, the author contends that politicians should be able to change their minds in light of new information or public opinion. However, u-turns may hurt a politician's credibility and convey the idea that special interests buy off politicians.

In Siddiqui's (2019) critical evaluation, the first year of PM Imran Khan's tenure is analyzed, emphasizing the government's inability to address critical issues effectively. The author attributes this shortcoming primarily to Khan's frequently changing stance on essential matters. The article centres on Khan's inadequacies in various crucial domains, such as economic development, safeguarding of human rights, and efficient governance. Siddiqui offers a critical assessment of the tax reform, civil-military relationships, and India-related policies of the Khan government, characterizing them as unfavourable policy developments. The government's reputation has been negatively impacted, and these U-turns have impeded its capacity to implement fundamental changes. The article expresses concern regarding the escalation of authoritarianism and intolerance in Pakistan, which has resulted in the infringement of human rights, curtailment of freedom of expression, and the suppression, persecution, and coercion of journalists and civil society activists.

According to Yousaf (2021), the PTI government faced significant criticism for its sudden shift in addressing various issues related to domestic, international, and economic policies. The aforementioned circumstance has instigated scepticism regarding the government's capacity to formulate judicial policy determinations and has been construed as substantiation of incompetence and a dearth of guidance. The frequency with which the government changes its stance indicates a need for more consistent and informed decision-making. Insufficient research before implementing significant policy changes has diminished the government's credibility and public trust. The government's reputation and authority have been negatively impacted due to public criticism regarding its lack of uniformity on crucial matters. The proclivity of the PTI administration to frequently alter their stances has resulted in a pervasive sense of ambiguity and disorder within the political landscape of Pakistan.

Afzal (2022) posits that the present political turmoil in Pakistan is a result of the intersection of economic and security issues. The essay delves into various factors contributing to the crisis, including the economic downturn, inflationary pressures, and growing societal dissatisfaction. The author discusses the military's political involvement and asserts that the armed forces have played a significant role in promoting democracy in Pakistan. For several decades, Pakistan's economy has been hindered by corruption, inefficiency, and inadequate investment. Terrorism and insurgency can be regarded as outward expressions of deeper socioeconomic and political factors, such as poverty and inequality, which give rise to political instability. This article evaluates the present political situation by analyzing the ruling government headed by PM Imran Khan and the opposing political factions. The argument posited by the author is that the task of presenting a plausible substitute to the present administration is a challenging one. This is because the government's economic and political programme has encountered resistance from influential vested interests. Furthermore, internal divisions and a dearth of public support have weakened the opposition parties.

The attainment of stability and progress in Pakistan is contingent upon resolving its political U-turns predicament. The nation's governing officials and decision-makers implement measures such as strengthening democratic establishments, upholding legal principles, and embracing a far-reaching strategic outlook. If such circumstances arise, reducing the effects of political reversals is possible. The attainment of stability and prosperity in Pakistan is contingent upon resolving the nation's underlying economic and security issues.

3. Political 'U-Turns' in Pakistan and Their Repercussions

The phenomenon of 'U-turns' has the potential to impact Pakistan's political landscape substantially. One potential consequence is the erosion of trust among the general public towards political figures and governmental institutions due to the dissemination of uncertain and contradictory information. Trust among individuals or groups may result in potential political instability, thereby impeding the growth and development of the nation. Moreover, making 'U-turns' could potentially result in a loss of trust among politicians, should voters perceive such actions as indicative of a shift in stance motivated by ulterior motives. The erosion of public trust in politicians can undermine their efficacy in enacting their proposed policies. The political climate in Pakistan is characterised by numerous parties and factions vying for power. Elected officials may face the temptation to prioritise short-term electoral gains through a reversal of policy, commonly known as a "U-turn," over pursuing long-term strategic objectives. This could result in formulating inadequately

deliberated policies that may have unforeseen ramifications for the country.

The phenomenon of U-turns holds considerable sway over the political landscape of Pakistan. Improving the transparency and accountability of the decision-making process could mitigate the adverse effects of policy reversals on a nation's economic and social progress. It is worth noting, however, that not all alterations in direction necessarily have detrimental consequences. Politicians must prioritize the long-term strategic goals of the nation and make decisions that align with the welfare of the populace.

4. Reiterate the Need to Address Pakistan's Political U-Turns

Political U-turns are a severe issue in Pakistan that need prompt attention. The hindrance of a nation's progress and stability, coupled with the erosion of public trust in the government, is observed. Given the significant impact on the country's economic and social well-being, partisan interests must be subordinated to the nation's long-term goals. Politicians must prioritize the welfare of their constituents and exhibit responsibility and transparency in making decisions. Implementing effective measures to address this matter would result in a more promising future for Pakistan, characterized by a government that prioritizes public service and fosters economic advancement and well-being.

5. Conclusions

The problem of political U-turns hampers Pakistan's progress towards peace and prosperity. In the realm of Pakistani politics, it is a frequent occurrence for policymakers to alter their course of action for a multitude of reasons. The lack of a comprehensive, enduring strategic outlook for the nation, the sway of extraneous factors and the pursuit of personal agendas constitute the fundamental underpinnings of policy reversals. The erosion of public trust in government and the weakening of democratic institutions can be attributed to the frequent policy shifts of political leaders and parties. The impact of the constrained economy has been experienced by business and social welfare domains, which are typically considered distinct from the realm of politics. The instability and uncertainty caused by policy reversals have highlighted the need for the government to enhance its ability to provide fundamental necessities such as healthcare and education to its citizens.

Pakistan's policymakers and political leaders must implement measures to mitigate the negative impact of U-turns on the country's political landscape. Establishing autonomous oversight entities, such as an unbiased and unrestricted media and an autonomous judiciary, and strategies to enhance transparency and responsibility in political decision-making are recommended. Implementing constitutional modifications, such as the establishment of an independent election commission and the decentralization of power to the regions, could potentially mitigate the sway of vested interest groups, enhance democratic institutions, and reinforce the principles of legal governance. In order to mitigate the impact of external factors and personal interests, it is imperative to enhance the economic state of Pakistan. In order to address the potential negative consequences of prioritizing immediate political gains, the political officials and decision-makers of the nation must establish a comprehensive and forward-thinking plan for the country's future. Developing a comprehensive strategy is imperative for ensuring national security and economic prosperity.

Pakistan's sustained progress and stability are contingent upon the nation's ability to confront the issue of political reversals. The mitigation of the destabilizing impact of political U-turns on Pakistan's stability and prosperity can be achieved by the implementation of recommended measures, including the reinforcement of democratic institutions and the rule of law, as well as the formulation of a comprehensive long-term strategic vision by the country's political leaders and policymakers.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

Not Applicable.

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